

Feature Article

Cleave and Couple: Toward fully sustainable catalytic conversion of lignocellulose to value added building blocks and fuels

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Abstract

The structural complexity of lignocellulose offers unique opportunities for the development of entirely new, energy efficient and waste-free pathways in order to obtain valuable bio-based building blocks. Such sustainable catalytic methods - specifically tailored to address the efficient conversion of abundant renewable starting materials - are necessary to successfully compete, in the future, with fossil-based multi-step processes. In this contribution we give a summary of recent developments in this field and describe our “cleave and couple” strategy, where “cleave” refers to the catalytic deconstruction of lignocellulose to aromatic and aliphatic alcohol intermediates, and “couple” involves the development of novel, sustainable transformations for the formation of C-C and C-N bonds in order to obtain a range of attractive products from lignocellulose.

1. Introduction

There is little doubt about the necessity of gradually transitioning from the use of fossil to renewable resources.^{1,2} This change will require the development of a whole array of novel catalytic transformations, both for upstream and downstream processing, which can accommodate the structural complexity of biopolymers as substrates³. A promising renewable raw material is lignocellulose that is produced as part of agricultural and forestry waste streams in large enough quantities globally to cover a substantial demand on chemical building blocks.^{4,5} Due to the considerable potential of lignocellulose to serve as alternative carbon supply, the efficient catalytic conversion of individual lignocellulose constituents was subject to intensive research. Much progress was achieved related to the valorization of the cellulose and hemicellulose fractions either upon conversion to bioethanol^{6,7} or to individual platform chemicals⁸⁻¹⁰. Promising directions were also identified regarding the depolymerization of the most challenging, lignin constituent.¹¹⁻¹⁶

Despite these remarkable advances, in order to achieve true economic feasibility of future biorefineries, it should be ensured that maximum value is derived from all individual lignocellulose components.^{16,17} This aspect has only been addressed more recently^{13,15,16}, since most methods focus exclusively on the valorization of either the cellulose or the lignin fraction after separation of these constituents by pretreatment.^{18,19} Furthermore, the

downstream processing of cellulose derived platform chemicals or intermediates emerging from new lignin depolymerization methods, still needs significant improvement in order to access sufficient diversity, ultimately covering an entire value pyramid of new bio-based products.

Importantly, any new research, creating technology for future implementation needs to be feasible for the conversion of large amount of renewable material. To reach the level of sustainability that is desired here, research questions need to be re-designed to maximize material balance, energy efficiency and sustainability globally. This should be achieved by implementing highly efficient, waste-free transformations in the individual reaction steps and catalysts that also rely on Earth-abundant metals.

Motivation

These considerations provided a key motive for establishing our independent research program starting in 2013, which focused on valorization of renewable resources by catalysis. Our approach recognizes that catalytic methods, which embrace the inherent complexity of renewable resources offer possibilities for the development of fully sustainable transformations.

Figure 1 From renewables to value added products via shorter, more sustainable pathways.

Earlier efforts mainly emphasize the extensive defunctionalisation of renewable starting materials in order to obtain simple bulk chemicals (e.g. BTX)^{14,20–22}. While the production of important bulk chemicals is desired, these strategies require large energy input to obtain structures that feed into conventional, frequently multistep processes (Figure 1). However,

especially when aiming for higher value products, which can enter the chemical supply chain at a much later stage than bulk chemicals, mild depolymerisation and controlled defunctionalisation of the structurally diverse starting materials is preferred. This requires less energy input and results in intermediates that retain *part* of the structural complexity inherent to the renewable substrate. Such new building blocks are ideally set up for the development of new atom-economic transformations, permitting their rapid conversion to higher value products directly, minimizing the number of overall reaction steps required, and significantly reducing the amount of waste formed. As an example, due to the high oxygen content of lignocellulosic biomass, mild depolymerization strategies should be designed so that they result in aliphatic or aromatic alcohols as intermediates. Subsequently, the development of fundamentally novel routes for the efficient and selective introduction of ammonia or simple amines would allow access to bio-based amines (Figure 2). The overall approach is not limited to these examples and there is ample inspiration for the development of other sustainable transformations that may provide alternative “shortcuts” to valuable bio-based products. In either case, research should focus on achieving a unique balance of “cleavage” and “coupling” pathways that would allow to access chemical diversity in products necessary to achieve economic competitiveness with current fossil fuel-based pathways.

Figure 2 General strategies for the sustainable production of amines from lignocellulose.

Naturally, the greatest challenge to achieve this very simple concept is to find suitable catalytic methods. Gratifyingly, doped porous metal oxides²³, which have previously shown widespread application turned out to be a marvelous choice. In this contribution we describe our work related to the flexible use copper doped porous metal oxides for the reductive depolymerization of lignocellulose to alcohol intermediates as well as other methods developed in our group for lignin depolymerization to aromatic intermediates. Subsequently, we show several strategies for the “coupling” of such intermediates focusing on the use of heterogeneous catalysts, such as doped metal oxides or commercially available catalysts.

2. Cleave – Depolymerization of lignocellulose and its constituents

Lignocellulose is a non-edible, renewable resource that consists of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. Different approaches have been developed to address the catalytic depolymerization of these individual constituents or lignocellulose as whole to smaller

molecules to be used as fuels or aliphatic and aromatic chemical building blocks.^{24–26} These strategies, targeting valorization of lignocellulose, are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Diverse ways of lignocellulose conversion: a.) Classical pretreatment focusing on obtaining high quality cellulose b.) Lignin isolation with stabilization using formaldehyde c.) One-pot catalytic conversion d.) Catalytic fractionation.

Classical biorefinery processes (Figure 3a) generally focus on energy intensive pre-treatment that involves the use of acid or other additives and relatively high temperatures in order to first separate lignocellulose to its main constituents.^{27,28,29} A well-established example is paper production by various pulping methods.^{30,31} These approaches typically result in high quality cellulose, which can be used as such for the production of fibers, paper, or subjected to enzymatic treatment to produce bioethanol, and impressive progress has been made in the catalytic or biocatalytic deconstruction of cellulose for the production of important platform chemicals. However, the lignin originating from these fractionation methods typically suffers from severe structural modification and contains more robust C-C bonds and much less cleavable β -O-4 linkages compared to native lignin and are therefore not ideal for further depolymerization, especially under mild conditions.¹³ Nonetheless, ample new knowledge was generated related to lignin depolymerization in various fields such as high temperature processes³², pyrolysis³³, heterogeneous³⁴, homogeneous catalysis³⁵ on model compounds and these were extensively reviewed.^{11,12,14} Among these, a number of original catalytic approaches have been developed that result in relatively high yield of aromatic monomers, as briefly discussed below. Furthermore, depolymerization via a “biological funneling” strategy was accomplished using enzymes.³⁶

Moreover, several groups developed novel, mild and more environmentally friendly lignin isolation methods that induce minimal structural degradation of lignin. Many of these use bio-renewable solvents (n-butanol³⁷, GVL³⁸ and THFA³⁹) and show great improvements for obtaining high-quality cellulose and lignin simultaneously from woody biomass.

A unique example, developed by the Luterbacher group (Figure 3b) was able to deliver high quality lignin by stabilization of its native structure via the formation of stable 1,3-dioxanes by addition of formaldehyde⁴⁰ or other aldehydes⁴¹ during organosolv pulping. Subsequent depolymerization of these isolated lignins provided near theoretical yields (47% -78%) of aromatics in the subsequent depolymerization by hydrogenolysis.

Organosolv lignin depolymerization

Several innovative strategies have been developed for the mild depolymerization of organosolv lignins such as oxidation⁴², hydrogen neutral⁴³, acid⁴⁴, reductive⁴⁵, photo⁴⁶ and/or electrocatalytic⁴⁷ approaches, as recently reviewed¹¹⁻¹⁶. Highly efficient depolymerisation of organosolv lignin could be also achieved via two-step methodologies include a selective peroxidation and subsequent reduction.⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ Generally, in these studies, individual lignin extraction methods were reported along with the catalytic depolymerization strategies, therefore direct comparison of yields is not precisely accurate. Our contribution to this field was the development of a concept which relies on lignin acidolysis in conjunction with the stabilization of reactive intermediates by adding ethylene glycol to obtain C2 ethylene glycol acetals upon acid catalysed cleavage^{37,52-55} (Figure 4). Stabilization of the reactive C2-aldehyde intermediates by catalytic methods such as hydrogenation and decarbonylation resulted in distinct classes of aromatics from model compounds and lignin.⁵³ All stabilization strategies resulted in suppressing recondensation reactions and the type of monomers obtained from lignin was the same as determined by model studies. Further effort was focused on increasing monomer yield by optimization of reaction conditions in the acidolysis/acetal formation method as well as the nature of the lignin used. Triflic acid was replaced by easy to handle metal triflates and the best result, ~20 wt% of C2 acetal yield, was obtained using Fe(OTf)₃ and walnut methanosolv lignin.⁵⁴ A separate study focused on evaluating the effect of various pre-treatment methods^{37,55} on the lignin structure and ultimately on aromatic monomer yields. Indeed, the observed aromatic monomer yield strongly depended on the content of cleavable β -O-4 units. While generally low yields were obtained with Kraft lignin, up to 35.5 wt% yield of C2 acetals could be reached using β -aryl ether rich organosolv lignin.

A common challenge in the development of new catalytic methods for lignin depolymerization is the lack of representative model compounds. New methods are either tested on overly simplified model compounds or lignin directly. The former approach is not representative enough and the latter may be associated with lengthy analytical procedures that prevent rapid evaluation of the new catalytic methods. Therefore we have developed scalable synthetic pathways for advanced, "next generation" lignin model compounds comprising the β -O-4- and the β -5 linkage as well as methoxy - or free phenol functionality.⁵²

Applying the previously developed acidolysis/ stabilization method on these models allowed for understanding lignin reactivity with excellent agreement between real lignin and model compound studies. This study also evaluated the reactivity of β -5 and β - β linkages. Globally,

it was found that the monomer units that are connected with an additional C-C bond are modified but not cleaved under these reaction conditions.⁵²

Figure 4 Summary of the work for production of lignin monomers by stabilization of C2 aldehydes.

One-pot processes

The direct conversion of the untreated lignocellulose in one-pot (Figure 3c) would circumvent the need for any pretreatment and significantly reduce the number of processing units (upstream) in a biorefinery, however the relatively complex product mixture obtained would shift the separation burden to the downstream processing stage. Moreover, the substantial structural difference between each component necessitates careful catalyst and process design. Different catalytic systems developed for a very efficient one-pot lignocellulose conversion are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Selected examples of total lignocellulose depolymerization through one-pot process.

Feedstock	Catalyst	General conditions	Main products and Yields	Ref.
Pine	Cu-PMO	Methanol, 320 °C, 8 h	C2-C6 alcohols and substituted cyclohexyl alcohols	56
Birch	Ni-W ₂ C/AC	Ethylene glycol, 235 °C, 6MPa H ₂ , 4 h	Phenols (46.5%) ^a Diols (-)	57
Ashtree	Ni-W ₂ C/AC	H ₂ O, 235 °C, 6MPa H ₂ , 4 h	Phenols (40.5%) ^a Diols (75.6%) ^b	57
Corn stalk	LiTaMoO ₆ + Ru/C + H ₃ PO ₄	H ₂ O, 230 °C, 6MPa H ₂ , 24 h	Phenols (35.7%) ^a Gasoline (82.4%) ^c	58
Corn cob	LiTaMoO ₆ + Ru/C + H ₃ PO ₄	H ₂ O, 230 °C, 6MPa H ₂ , 24 h	Phenols (53.0%) ^a Gasoline (58.4%) ^c	58
Birch	Pt/NbOPO ₄	Cyclohexane, 190 °C, 5MPa H ₂ , 20 h	Pentanes (10.2 wt%) ^d , hexanes (13.1 wt%) ^e and alkylcyclohexanes (4.8 wt%) ^f	59

^a Phenol Yield = (mass of carbon in phenol)/(mass of carbon in lignin)

^b Diol Yield = (mass of carbon in diol)/(total mass of carbon in cellulose & hemicellulose)

^c Gasoline Yield = (mass of carbon in C₅-C₆ alkanes)/(total mass of carbon in cellulose & hemicellulose)

^d Pentanes Yield = (mass of pentanes)/(mass of hemicellulose)

^e Hexanes Yield = (mass of Hexanes)/(mass of cellulose)

^f Alkylcyclohexanes Yield = (mass of alkylcyclohexanes)/(mass of lignin)

Ford and coworkers pioneered the use of copper-doped porous metal oxides (Cu-PMO) as catalysts for the one-pot conversion of lignocellulose in supercritical methanol.^{23,60,56} Notably, the hydrogen equivalents needed for depolymerization and further hydrodeoxygenation processes originated from methanol upon reforming. Lignocellulose solids were converted to combustible liquids and little or no char was formed. The products of the liquid phase were generally (C2 to C6) aliphatic alcohols and ethers from the cellulose and hemicellulose fraction and largely (C9–C12) cyclohexanol derivatives originating from the lignin fraction.

Zhang and co-workers described a one-pot reductive process using a carbon supported Ni–W₂C catalyst in water.⁵⁷ In this case, the carbohydrate fraction of lignocellulose was converted to ethylene glycol as well as other diols with a total yield of up to 75.6%, while the lignin component was converted selectively into propyl- and propanol-substituted methoxy-phenols with a yield of 46.5% at 235 °C under 60 bar hydrogen when using birch. The inexpensive Ni-W₂C/AC exhibited an activity competitive activity with noble metal catalysts (Pd, Pt, Ru and Ir).

Ma and co-workers successfully converted raw biomass into gasoline alkanes (hexanes and pentanes from cellulose and hemicellulose, respectively) and alkylated methoxy-phenols (from lignin) over layered LiTaMoO₆ and Ru/C in an aqueous medium also containing phosphoric acid.⁵⁸

In 2016, Wang and co-workers produced liquid alkanes from various lignocellulose sources by a one-pot process over a Pt/NbOPO₄ catalyst in cyclohexane, with ample structural characterization of the catalyst.⁵⁹ With this multifunctional catalyst the direct hydrodeoxygenation of lignocellulose under mild conditions (190 °C) lead to liquid alkanes with mass yields up to 28.1 wt% in cyclohexane.

“Lignin first” approaches - Aromatics in high yield

Recently an elegant approach that combines lignin extraction with depolymerization has been introduced (Figure 3d). During this process, lignocellulose fractionation is performed in the presence of a heterogeneous catalyst, typically under reductive atmosphere (using H₂ or hydrogen donor).⁶¹ This particular process, frequently referred to as “lignin first”⁶¹, was signified by various terms in recent literature as: Reductive Catalytic Fractionation (RCF)^{62–64}, Early-stage Catalytic Conversion of Lignin (ECCL)^{65–67}, Catalytic Upstream Biorefining (CUB)^{65,66} or hydrogenolysis of protolignin^{68,69}.

The great advantage of this process is that native lignin, which is solvolytically extracted from lignocellulose, is immediately depolymerized to aromatic monomers before it has the chance to undergo extensive structural modification. Upon RCF, a liquid and solid fraction are obtained. The former contains a set of aromatic monomers (shown below on Figure 5) dissolved in the reaction solvent, while the latter contains solid carbohydrate pulp mixed with the catalyst. Because of this, catalyst separation and the valorization of the carbohydrate fraction is also very important to address as discussed further below.

Many research groups have used the RCF strategy and applied various reaction conditions in order to maximize delignification and the yield of aromatic monomers. These advances were comprehensively reviewed and a list of selected reaction conditions and corresponding products and yields are shown in Table 2. Typically commercially available heterogeneous catalysts on carbon supports such as Pd/C, Ru/C, Rh/C or Ni/C were used^{63,68–72}. A variety of solvents^{73,74} as well as several additives^{75–77} were explored for studying the effect on delignification and influencing monomer yield and the overall efficiency of the process. Notably, a flow-through setup⁶² for this method was also reported, showing the possibility of continuous production of lignin monomers. Moreover, a hydrogen-free RCF process was developed where hemicellulose was used as a hydrogen source for lignin depolymerization by transfer hydrogenolysis over a commercial Pd/C catalyst.⁷⁸

Figure 5 Summary of monomers obtained by RCF from various methods. For yields and conditions see Table 2.

Table 2 Reductive catalytic fractionation of lignocellulose^{a, b, c, d}

Entry	Feedstock	Catalyst	Reaction conditions			Sugar retention	Yield of main products	Total Monomer Yield ^a	Year ^{ref.}	
			Solvent	T (°C)	P (bar)					T (h)
1	Maple	Raney Ni + NaOH	Dioxane/ H ₂ O (1:1)	173	H ₂ (210)	6	N. R. ^b	3S (15.4 wt%)	27.3 wt%	1948 ⁷⁹
2	Aspen	Raney Ni	Dioxane/ H ₂ O (1:1)	220	H ₂ (35)	5	N. R.	2S (28.5 wt%), 1S (12.7 wt%)	59.1 wt%	1963 ⁸⁰
3	Aspen	Rh/C	Dioxane/ H ₂ O (1:1)	195	H ₂ (34)	5	N. R.	2S (12.9 wt%), 1S (25.6 wt%)	50.1 wt%	1978 ⁸¹
4	Birch	H ₃ PO ₄ + Pt/C	Dioxane/ H ₂ O (1:1)	200	H ₂ (40)	4	N. R.	2S (21.1 wt%), 1S (14.5 wt%)	46.5 wt%	2008 ⁸²
5	Pine	Pd/C	Dioxane/ H ₂ O (1:1)	195	H ₂ (34.5)	24	N. R.	1G (20.8 wt%)	22.4 wt%	2011 ⁸³
6	Birch	Ni/C	Methanol	200	Ar (1)	6	N. R.	2S (36.2 wt%), 2G (11.9 wt%)	54 wt%	2013 ⁸⁴
7	Birch	Pd/C	Ethanol/ H ₂ O (1:1)	195	Ar (4)	1	N. R.	5S (49%)	49 % (C-Yield)	2014 ⁸⁵
8	Birch	Ru/C	Methanol	250	H ₂ (30)	6	81 % (C-Yield)	2S (30.5 wt%), 2G (10.4 wt%)	51.5% (C-Yield)	2015 ⁸⁶
9	Poplar	Zn/Pd/C	Methanol	225	H ₂ (34.5)	12	79 wt%	2S (29.7 wt%), 2G (24.3 wt%)	54 wt%	2015 ⁷¹
10	Birch	Pd/C	Methanol	250	H ₂ (30)	3	89 % (C-Yield)	1S (35.2 wt%), 1G (9.7 wt%)	49.3 % (C-Yield)	2015 ⁶⁹

Entry	Feedstock	Catalyst	Reaction conditions				Sugar retention	Yield of main products	Total Monomer Yield ^a	Year ^{ref.}
			Solvent	T (°C)	P (bar)	T (h)				
11	Birch	Ni/C	Methanol	200	N ₂ (2)	6	N. P.	2S (18 wt%), 2G (10 wt%)	32 wt%	2015 ⁸⁶
12	Cedar	H ₂ SO ₄	Toluene/Methanol	170	Air	0.1	N. P.	8G (5.4 wt%)	10 wt%	2015 ⁸⁷
13	Birch	Pd/C	Ethanol/H ₂ O (1:1)	210	Ar	15	84.4 wt%	2S (20 wt%), 5S (11 wt%)	36 % (C-Yield)	2016 ⁷⁸
14	Poplar	H ₃ PO ₄ + Pd/C	Methanol	200	H ₂ (20)	3	72 wt%	1S (21 %), 1G (14 %)	42 % (C-Yield)	2016 ⁷⁵
15	Miscanthus	Ni/C	Methanol	225	H ₂ (60)	12	86 wt%	2S (19 wt%), 2G (21 wt%), 4G (12 wt%), 4S (16 wt%)	68 wt%	2016 ⁷⁰
16	Beech	Ni/C	Methanol/H ₂ O (3:2)	200	H ₂ (60)	5	N. P.	1S (28.9 wt%), 1G (9.8 wt%)	51.4 wt%	2016 ⁸⁸
17	Poplar	Pd/C	Methanol/H ₂ O (7:3)	200	H ₂ (20)	3	~66.7 wt%	1S (21.5 wt%), 1G (14.0 wt%)	43.5 wt%	2016 ⁷³
18	Poplar	Pd/C	Ethanol/H ₂ O (1:1)	200	H ₂ (20)	3	~73.2 wt%	1S (21.5 wt%), 1G (14.2 wt%)	43.3 wt%	2016 ⁷³
19	Birch	Pd/C	H ₂ O	200	H ₂ (30)	3	55 wt%	1S (31.6 wt%), 1G (7.9 wt%)	43.8 wt%	2016 ⁷⁴
20	Corn Stover	Ni/C	Methanol	200	H ₂ (30)	3	76 wt%	7G (7.2 wt%), 7P (8.7 wt%)	24.5 wt%	2016 ⁶⁴
21	Birch	Pd/C + Al(OTf) ₃	Methanol	180	H ₂ (30)	2	76.5 wt%	6G (8.4 wt%), 6S (33.8 wt%)	55 wt%	2017 ⁷⁷
22	Oak	Pd/C + Al(OTf) ₃	Methanol	180	H ₂ (30)	2	76.6 wt%	6S (11.5 wt%), 1S (9.9 wt%)	46 wt%	2017 ⁷⁶
23	Birch	NiFe/C	Methanol	200	H ₂ (20)	6	N. R.	2S (23.70 wt%), 2G (11.06 wt%)	39.5 wt%	2017 ⁷²
24 ^c	Birch	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	Methanol	250	H ₂ (30)	3	84.9 wt%	1S+ 1G (21 wt%)	36 wt%	2017 ⁶³
25 ^d	Birch	Pd/C + H ₃ PO ₄	Methanol/H ₂ O (7:3)	180	H ₂ (30)	3	~56 wt%	1S+1G (18.2 wt%)	37 wt%	2017 ⁶²

^aYield calculated based on lignin content in each wood. ^bN. R. means not reported. ^cNi/Al₂O₃ pellets in basket.

^dReaction operated in a flow-through system.

Conversion of the carbohydrate fraction and catalyst recycling

Efficient recuperation of the heterogeneous catalyst that remains mixed with the carbohydrate pulp after RCF is a crucial factor for establishing economic viability of future lignin-first biorefineries.⁶¹ In this context, several approaches have been reported (shown on Figure 6),¹⁵ which include the use of magnetically separable catalysts⁸⁹, the use of a microporous catalyst cage^{63,70,71} for physical separation of the catalyst from the pulp as well as liquid-liquid extraction.⁷⁴ The simple further treatment of the solid residue, typically in order to gain soluble sugars was also studied and further catalytic conversion of the pulp to polyols⁶⁸, sugars^{62,64,71,78}, platform chemicals such as levulinic acid and furfural⁷⁰, or enzymatic fermentation to obtain ethanol⁶³ were also reported (Table 3).

Table 3 Selected examples of total lignocellulose utilization through RCF process.

Feedstock	Catalyst (1st step)	General conditions (1st step)	Main products	Lignin monomer yield	Sugar retention	Catalyst (2nd step)	General conditions (2nd step)	Main products and Ref. yield
Birch	Ru/C	Methanol, 250 °C, H ₂	2G, 2S	52 C%	81 C%	Ru/C + Tungstosilicic Acid	H ₂ O, 190 °C, H ₂	Sorbitol, Xylitol (89%) ⁶⁸
Birch	Ni-Al ₂ O ₃	Methanol, 250 °C, H ₂	1G, 1S	44 C%	85 wt%	GSE16-T18-HAA1* yeast	citrate buffer, 35 °C	Bio-ethanol (73%) ⁶³
Poplar WT-LORRE	Pd/Zn/C	Methanol, 225 °C, H ₂	2G, 2S	54 wt%	79 wt%	CTEC cellulase	H ₂ O, 50 °C	Glucose (95%) ⁷¹
Miscanthus	Ni/C	Methanol, 225 °C, H ₂	2G, 2S	68 wt%	86 wt%	FeCl ₃	H ₂ O/MeTHF, 200 °C (MW)	LA (76%), FF (55%) ⁷⁰
Corn Stover	Ni/C	Methanol, 200 °C, H ₂	7G, 7P	24.5 wt%	97 wt%	CTec3 and HTec3 Enzyme	50 °C in sodium acetate	Soluble sugars ⁶⁴
Birch	Pd/C	Ethanol/H ₂ O, 210 °C, Ar	2G, 5G	36 C%	84 wt%	Accellerase TRIO	50 °C in sodium citrate buffer	Glucose (41%) ⁷⁸
Birch	Pd/C +	Methanol/H ₂ O, 180	1G, 1S	37 wt%	~56 wt%	Cellulase	acetate buffer	Glucose (95%) ⁶²

Poplar	H ₃ PO ₄ Cu20-PMO	°C Methanol, 180 °C, H ₂	1G, 1S	36 wt%	-	Cu20-PMO	sodium azide Methanol, 320 °C	Mixture of alcohols	90
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For example, Sels and co-workers separated the carbohydrate pulp (contained up to 92% of the initial polysaccharides) from the Ru/C catalyst after RCF, and subsequently converted this fraction to sugar polyols with addition of a tungstosilicic acid catalyst in water, at 190 °C, under reductive atmosphere.⁶⁸

Furthermore, the use of microporous cage (325 meshes) with a Zn/Pd/C catalyst⁷¹ or a reactor basket filled with catalyst pellets (Ni-Al₂O₃, 1.2 × 3 mm)⁶³ during RCF both resulted in efficient removal of the catalyst from the pulp and recycling (Figure 6c). The same separation method was also applied with Ni/C catalyst to yield up to 68% of aromatic products from lignin and in this case, the solid residue was converted into furfural and levulinic acid using earth-abundant iron salts.⁷⁰

Figure 6 Catalyst recuperation strategies in RCF process.

Recently, Samec and co-workers developed a in a flow-through system⁶² (Figure 7) in which the pulping and transfer hydrogenolysis steps were separated in time and space. This setup included a percolation reactor filled with woody biomass and a fixed catalytic bed reactor filled with Pd/C and resulted in 37 wt% of aromatic compounds. And this system also gave a very easy separation of the cellulose fraction that could be enzymatically hydrolysed to glucose (87 wt% yield) without purification.

Figure 7 Schematic representation of the flow through system used for RCF process. Reprinted with permission from ref⁶². Copyright 2017 Royal Society of Chemistry.

Anderson et al. have developed a system in which a flow through, single-bed reactor and a flow through dual-bed reactor were connected.⁹¹ In contrast to batch processes, this flow

system allowed for facile collection of time-resolved data for both lignin extraction and hydrogenolysis products. The use of multi-bed RCF experiments made a catalyst deactivation study possible, which showed that leaching, sintering, and surface poisoning were the main reasons for decreased catalytic performance.

The LignoFlex process

Following the “cleave and couple” motive, and inspired by the catalytic reductive fractionation methods⁸⁶, we set to develop a novel approach that would lead to aromatic and aliphatic intermediates in two consecutive steps of a lignocellulose conversion process (Figure 8). These should be ideally set up for establishing a desired follow up chemistry that would lead to a broader diversity of attractive products ranging from bulk to specialized building blocks. The divergent functionalization of lignin derived aromatics has not yet been thoroughly addressed in the field. Importantly, we aimed for full conversion of solid residues and integrated catalyst recycling. Clearly, the key here was to find an appropriate catalyst.

Figure 8 Desired flexible use of Cu-20PMO catalyst in a two lignocellulose conversion process with integrated catalyst recycling (*LignoFlex*).⁹⁰

Copper doped porous metal oxides

Hydrotalcites are versatile materials for various catalytic applications (Figure 9a) that can be easily prepared by co-precipitation of metal salts in aqueous solution.^{92–94} Their structure and properties are modular and can be easily tailored by the right selection of the type and amount of the respective $[M^{2+}]$ and $[M^{3+}]$ metals and dopants (e.g. below for the Guerbet reaction and C-C bond formation). Porous metal oxide catalysts are high surface area materials, which are obtained by calcination of synthetic hydrotalcites.

Copper doped porous metal oxides (Cu-PMOs)²³, which have previously shown widespread application in catalysis (Figure 9b), appeared to be a marvelous choice for the development of the above mentioned total catalytic valorization concept.⁹⁰ These catalysts are derived from synthetic Mg/Al-HTC (Mg: Al= 3:1) whereby 20% of the Mg^{2+} cations are substituted by Cu^{2+} ions. Beside high surface area and basicity, the Cu dopant is responsible for the increased hydrogenation/dehydrogenation and hydrogenolysis activity⁹⁵ of this material as described further below.

The Ford group has introduced the use of Cu-PMOs for the catalytic conversion of various lignocellulose-derived materials. In 2009, the catalytic hydrogenolysis of the ether C-O bond and subsequent hydrogenation of the aromatic ring in the simple lignin model compound

dihydrobenzofuran (DHBF) in supercritical methanol was described.⁶⁰ Other studies, related to the reactivity of simple lignin model compounds were also conducted.⁹⁶ Notably, the hydrogen equivalents for the reductive depolymerization and hydrogenation events, were generated from the reaction solvent itself, which under the reaction conditions underwent reforming to hydrogen and carbon-monoxide. Subsequently, the very efficient catalytic deconstruction of poplar lignin to cyclic aliphatic alcohols was accomplished with this method⁹⁷. In addition, the holistic evaluation of the obtained product mixtures by ¹H NMR spectroscopy was developed.⁹⁷ Later, the complete catalytic conversion of lignocellulose solids without any formation of intractable side products (char) was achieved by this single stage, methanol mediated process.^{23,56} The liquid products contained predominantly (C2-C6 and C9-C12) aliphatic alcohols and ethers, which originated from the cellulose and the lignin constituent of lignocellulose.

Next, the Cu₂O-PMO was used for the depolymerization of Candlenut lignin under milder reaction conditions (140°C-220°C, 30-60 bar H₂) in methanol as solvent, a method that allowed for isolation of single aromatic products upon depolymerization⁹⁸.

This catalyst was furthermore used in the conversion of 5-hydroxymethyl furfural (5-HMF) to 2,5-dimethylfuran (DMF) in supercritical methanol⁹⁹ or to DMF and 2,5-furan dimethanol (FDM) at lower temperatures¹⁰⁰ and was successfully applied for the upgrading of pyrolysis oil sugar fractions.¹⁰¹

Figure 9 Reported application of copper doped porous metal oxides (Cu-PMO) in the catalytic conversion of biomass and related transformations.

Lignin-derived aromatic alcohols

Based on the unique reactivity of Cu-20PMO under mild and supercritical conditions detailed above, we set to demonstrate our novel two stage catalytic lignocellulose conversion process combined with catalyst recycling.⁹⁰ First, we aimed to establish suitable RCF conditions to gain aromatics from lignin by using pine lignocellulose and Cu-20PMO in methanol, in the temperature range of 140-220 °C. Gratifyingly, under optimized reaction

conditions (180 °C, 18 h, 40 bar H₂), gas chromatography analysis of the methanol soluble fraction revealed an almost exclusive (90%) formation of 4-propanolguaiacol (**1G**), which could also be isolated as pure compound (Figure 10a). Mechanistic investigations using model compounds preliminarily suggest that the depolymerization proceeds via hydrogenolysis of the phenyl-ether bonds in the β-O-4 lignin moiety, either via a sequence of dehydrogenation/hydrogenolysis or direct hydrogenolysis event in the presence of hydrogen gas.

It should be noted, that typically Ru/C or Pd/C have been used, generally above 200 °C, which typically delivered 4-alkyl phenols due to the higher hydrogenolysis activity of these noble metal catalysts. Several examples with Ni catalyst have been reported since, especially a Ni catalyst in combination with pre-stabilization of the lignin at extraction resulted in high yields and selectivity of **1G**, however no copper-based catalyst has been developed for RCF prior to our work.

Subsequently, a variety of wood species were successfully converted to typically 2-3 main products. Higher yields were obtained with poplar (36%), beech (31%), and maple (30%). A good correlation between the S/G ratio of the lignin extracted from these sources, and the S/G ratio of the product mixture was observed (Figure 10c). Interestingly, from 1 g maple wood both the 4-propanolsyringol (**1S**, 31 mg) and 4-propanolguaiacol (**1G**, 22 mg) could be isolated.

Figure 10 a). Composition of products obtained from various lignocellulose sources. 1st step: mild 2nd step: supercritical. b). GC-FID image of the products after 1st step reaction using poplar as feedstock. c). Relationship between the S/G ratio of isolated lignin and monomer products from various wood lignocelluloses.

After obtaining aromatics by mild reductive treatment of lignocellulose described above, the reaction solids consisting of unreacted lignocellulose and catalyst, were subjected to catalytic treatment in supercritical methanol (320 °C) in the presence of *in situ* formed hydrogen, which gratifyingly resulted in full conversion of the cellulose rich residues and the catalyst was liberated for re-use. The composition of the obtained clear, colorless methanol solutions from different wood samples was largely similar and consisted predominantly of aliphatic alcohols, small amounts of ethers and esters, as well as minor amounts of alkyl-phenols (Figure 10a). Efficient catalyst recycling for 5 consecutive mild and supercritical runs was demonstrated using pine lignocellulose (Figure 11). Minimal leaching was observed and the loss of catalyst activity in the 9th and 10th supercritical experiment was attributed to the aggregation of Mg and Al by TEM measurements.

Figure 11 a). General scheme for complete conversion of pine lignocellulose to aromatic and aliphatic alcohols through the flexible use of Cu₂₀-PMO with integrated catalytic recycling. b).

Composition of products obtained from recycling tests. 1st step: mild. 2nd step: supercritical. Reproduced with permission from ref. ⁹⁰ Copyright 2018 Springer Nature.

3. Couple – From alcohol intermediates to value added products via C-C and C-N bond formation

The *LignoFlex* process resulted in the formation of aromatic alcohol intermediate from lignin and a mixture of aliphatic alcohols from the cellulose portion of lignocellulosic biomass. In our view, the beauty of this approach is that these alcohols are ideally set up for a number of attractive, atom-economic transformations involving the formation of carbon-carbon and carbon-oxygen bonds (Figure 12). This allows reaching valuable products with minimal number of reaction steps and with minimal formation of waste.

Figure 12 Strategies for the catalytic conversion of alcohol intermediates obtained by the *LignoFlex* process. Reproduced with permission from ref. ⁹⁰. Copyright 2018 Springer Nature.

3.1 Upgrading lignocellulose derived chemicals through C–C coupling reactions

From cellulose derived alcohols to long chain alkanes

Given the complexity of the product mixtures obtained upon the supercritical methanol treatment, a convergent strategy towards obtaining products of uniform composition seemed most ideal. This should be first achieved by elongation of the relatively short chain length (C2-C6) alcohols via C-C bond formation, followed by deoxygenation to deliver transportation range alkanes (Figure 13). The challenge is great because there are no examples for the coupling of such relatively complex mixture of alkanes via C-C bond formation.

The potential of lignocellulose derived chemicals to be used as liquid transportation fuels or additives, has been extensively reviewed^{102–107}. More specifically, the production of Jet-fuel range alkanes from the important sugar derived platform chemicals 5-HMF or furfural via various chain elongation methods followed by exhaustive hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) was studied extensively.¹⁰³ For example, 5-HMF was shown to undergo aldol cross condensation with acetone followed by ring opening and deoxygenation to result in the formation of C9-C16 alkanes.^{108,109} Furfural can participate in analogous pathways, for example with ketones^{110,111} and bioalcohols¹¹² to ultimately deliver fuels.

Cyclopentanone has a cyclic structure and can be obtained in very high yield from furfural.^{113–118} Recently, it was found to be a building block for the synthesis of diesel and jet-fuel range cycloalkanes^{119–124}. For example, from the hydroxyalkylation/alkylation (HAA) of cyclopentanone with 2-methylfuran followed by hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) a mixture of C9-C15 branched alkanes and cycloalkanes can be produced.¹²⁵ It was also reported that high-density (0.82 g mL⁻¹) jet-fuel range cycloalkanes can be synthesized in high overall yields (~80%) by the aldol condensation of cyclopentanone and butanal followed by hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) reaction.¹²⁶ The related cyclopentanol was reported to undergo the Guerbet coupling to result in C10 cyclic alkanes upon HDO.¹²⁷

Lastly, the acetone, n-butanol, ethanol (ABE) mixture, which can be obtained via fermentation from sugars or even lignocellulose^{128–130} has been shown to undergo a dehydrogenation/aldol condensation/hydrogenation sequence to form chain elongated ketones, which upon HDO resulted in the formation of C5-C11 alkanes as transportation range fuels.¹³¹ Several heterogeneous catalysts were developed for this transformation¹³², such as a Pd/Cu doped hydrotalcites,¹³³ 2.5% Cu doped hydrotalcites prepared by impregnation,¹³⁴ Pd@C with CaO as a solid base,¹³⁵ or a Ni-MgO-SiO₂ catalyst with improved water resistance for the highly selective conversion of solventless ABE mixtures to C5-C15 ketones and alcohols at 240 °C.¹³⁶

Figure 13 Summary of catalytic processes for the production of jet fuel range alkanes via C-C bond formation and HDO reactions.

Guerbet-coupling of cellulose derived alcohols

The Guerbet-coupling was most extensively investigated for the transformation of ethanol^{137,138,139} to 1-butanol as it has a higher energy density (ca. 90% that of gasoline), lower miscibility with water and lower heat of vaporization.^{106,140} As shown in Figure 14, beside the desired Guerbet-pathway, a number of side reactions exist during this transformation, rendering selective formation of n-butanol challenging. Therefore, careful catalyst design is of key importance in order to suppress the dehydration and Tishchenko pathways that lead to the formation of diethylether and ethyl-acetate side products, respectively.^{106,141}

Figure 14 Reaction network for the Guerbet coupling of ethanol showing the main reaction and side reactions.

Several heterogeneous catalysts were reported including MgO¹⁴², Mg/Al mixed metal oxides¹⁴³, hydroxyapatites^{144,145} and supported metal catalysts^{146–148}. Mechanistic studies pointed out the importance of surface properties, especially acidity and basicity for the influence of several key reaction steps, including ethanol dehydrogenation. Mg/Al mixed metal oxide catalysts derived from hydrotalcite precursors have attracted attention due to their high surface area, tuneable acid–base properties, and structural stability.¹⁰⁴

Figure 15 Evaluation of different PMO compositions in the Guerbet reaction of ethanol to 1-butanol. Reaction conditions: catalyst (100 mg), ethanol (3 mL), 6 h, 310 °C, decane (20 μL). Reprinted with permission from ref.¹⁴⁹. Copyright 2017 American Chemical Society.

We have systematically studied the performance of several metal doped hydrotalcite derived PMO catalysts, including the Cu-20PMO used before (Figure 15). Replacing a small portion of Mg²⁺ with Cu and Ni simultaneously resulted in catalyst composition that showed high selectivity for the formation of 1-butanol and negligible formation of ethyl-acetate. The conversion of ethanol increased from 30.8% for the undoped material to 62.4% for the

Cu13Ni7-PMO catalyst and yield in 1-butanol from 5.6 to 21.7% for the Cu10Ni10-PMO catalyst.

Coupling of challenging alcohol mixtures

Considering that our products obtained upon supercritical treatment are predominantly C2-C4 alcohols, we argued that simple Guerbet coupling would not result in long enough chain length alkanes. Therefore we selected cyclopentanone as suitable, stable coupling partner. Inspired by the aldol condensation pathways involving cyclopentanone and butanal as well as the hydrogen-borrowing – aldol condensation sequence carried out with ABE mixtures (Figure 13), we aimed to establish the efficient coupling of pentanol model compound with cyclopentanone. Due to its good dehydrogenation activity but low tendency for the Tishchenko pathways, the CuNi-PMO catalyst developed earlier for the Guerbet reaction gave superior performance for establishing the desired dehydrogenation – aldol condensation – hydrogenation sequence. Importantly, a 10 component equimolar alcohol model mixture could also be efficiently coupled to obtain the corresponding long chain ketones (Figure 16). Here, several differences in reactivity became apparent and branched primary alcohols as well as cyclic secondary alcohols remained intact. The amount of obtained long chain cyclic ketones was deemed appropriate, we decided to optimize reaction conditions directly using the real, lignocellulose residue mixture. However, first no reaction was observed.

Figure 16 Establishing novel coupling methodology of pentanol with cyclopentanone and a 10 component model mixture.

After several attempts it was identified that the methanol solvent was hampering the coupling reaction. Therefore, an elaborate solvent exchange procedure was developed, which resulted in retaining most of the mixture components in heptane. Successful coupling of these components resulted in the formation of a mixture of long chain ketones under elevated temperatures. A robust hydrodeoxygenation procedure using the commercially available Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ delivered clean mixtures of alkanes (Figure 17a).

^a Yield A = Total Alkanes / (Pine solid residue + Cyclopentanone); Yield B = (Total Alkanes - Cyclopentanone) / Pine solid residue

Figure 17 a). GC-MS image of alkanes from alcohol mixture obtained via supercritical methanol treatment of lignocellulose residues. b). Carbon weights of starting material and alkane products as well as total carbon yields. Reproduced with permission from ref. ⁹⁰. Copyright 2018 Springer Nature.

The alkane products obtained can be divided into two categories: C₄-C₆ range alkanes originating from branched or cyclic alcohols that were not coupled and C₈-C₁₁ alkanes from the coupling of cyclopentanone with aliphatic alcohols in the starting material and of lignin-derived propyl-cyclohexanols with total yield of 54% (Figure 17b).

3.2 Upgrading lignocellulose derived chemicals through C-N coupling reactions

The development of novel catalytic methods that enable the formation of amines from readily available aliphatic or aromatic alcohol intermediates generated by the catalytic conversion of renewable resources^{150,151} such as lignocellulose^{23,152,153} or via fermentation¹⁵⁴ are of utmost importance, since amines are at the core of the chemical industry. Primary and secondary amine moieties are omnipresent in natural products, bioactive molecules and pharmaceutical products, agrochemicals^{155,156}. Importantly, amines are also frequently encountered as building blocks for the synthesis of polymers that are produced in large scale annually.^{157,158} A very interesting and comprehensive review on this subject was recently published by Sels and co-workers.¹⁵⁹ In addition, several reviews summarized the challenges associated with using ammonia and homogeneous catalysts.¹⁶⁰⁻¹⁶² In the

following section, we will focus on heterogeneous catalytic systems using ammonia as nitrogen source.

The aromatic compound (4-propanol-guaiacol) **1G** could be obtained in very high selectivity and good yield and as pure compound directly from lignocellulose (Figure 11) and we and others have proposed that it may serve as lignin derived platform chemical.⁹⁰ However to this end, it needs to be established that the structure of **1G** is versatile enough for further functionalization and that its conversion leads to valuable, tangible products. Again, the aliphatic and aromatic alcohol functionality proved as suitable handle for further functionalization. We primarily focused on incorporating nitrogen via the borrowing hydrogen method on the aliphatic end using heterogeneous catalyst. The phenol moiety was converted via homogeneous and stoichiometric methods to aniline or derivatives.

Primary amines

Amines, especially primary amines are important intermediates but obtaining these selectively by alkylation of ammonia from alcohols is challenging because they are generally more reactive than ammonia itself.¹⁶³ Catalytic systems for coupling ammonia and alcohols using heterogeneous catalysts normally suffer from drawbacks such as low selectivity¹⁶⁴ and the need for high temperature (>200 °C) or elevated pressure of H₂ or NH₃.¹⁶⁵ So the development of more efficient heterogeneous or homogeneous catalyst systems that enable the amination reaction to proceed under milder conditions and tolerate various biomass-derived substrates is desired.

Several catalytic systems based on noble-metal catalysts have been developed that show high activity and selectivity. For example, Murzin and co-workers investigated the direct amination of dodecanol with ammonia to dodecylamine under various ammonia and hydrogen pressures over Ru/C, Pd/C, Pt/C, Ir/C and Os/C catalysts.¹⁶⁶ High yields of the desired 1-dodecylamine (>70%) were achieved over Ru/C and Pd/C catalysts. Rose and co-workers presented a one-pot amination of various biogenic alcohols using Ru/C as a solid catalyst in water.¹⁶⁷ Remarkably, they found water to be a suitable solvent for the sustainable production of biogenic amines. Mizuno and co-workers synthesized various types of “tertiary” amines (even unsymmetrically substituted ones) via the N-alkylation of ammonia (or its surrogates) and amines with primary alcohols by supported ruthenium hydroxide catalyst Ru(OH)_x/TiO₂.¹⁶⁸

The reaction of diols with amines is also attractive and more challenging as the main products with diols as starting materials, especially for C₄–C₆ diols, are N-heterocyclic compounds because cyclization reaction is thermodynamically favoured. In 1997, Baiker and co-workers¹⁶⁹ presented a comprehensive study on the heterogeneous catalytic transformations of bi- and polyfunctional alcohols to the corresponding linear and branched (but not cyclic) amines. The catalysts developed included supported metal and multimetallic hydrogenation catalysts and solid acids. The reaction mechanisms according to the different types of catalysts were also discussed. In 2014, Tomishige and co-workers reported the amination of various C₃ alcohols such as 1,2-propanediol with ammonia by Rh-In/C in

water.¹⁷⁰ In this research, Rh/C was found totally inactive; however the addition of Indium increased the activity of the catalyst in the dehydrogenation of alcohols, especially in the presence of amine or ammonia. Rh-In alloy particles with the size of 3-4 nm were formed and amino alcohols were obtained in 68% total selectivity at 38% conversion of 1,2-propanediol. Zhao and co-workers¹⁷¹ developed an environmental friendly route to produce hexamethylenediamine (HMDA) - an important reagent for the synthesis of Nylon-6,6, via catalytic amination of 1,6-hexanediol in the presence of hydrogen. The activities of supported Ni, Co, Ru, Pt, Pd catalysts were investigated in supercritical ammonia without any additives and Ru/Al₂O₃ presented the best result for the desired product of HMDA with yield of 38.4%.

In 2017, Zhang and co-workers¹⁷² developed the reductive amination of various biomass-derived aldehydes/ketones in aqueous ammonia under mild reaction conditions using a Ru/ZrO₂ catalyst. The catalyst comprised metallic active sites (Ru) for imine hydrogenation as well as acid sites (ZrO₂) for activation of carbonyl groups that are believed to be responsible for the excellent performance for the production of primary amines. As shown in Figure 18, good to excellent yields of primary amines were obtained. This included ethanolamine, a large-market nitrogen-containing chemical in a two-step approach from lignocellulose in an overall yield of 10%.

Figure 18 Amination of various aldehydes/ketones in aqueous ammonia by Ru/ZrO₂ catalyst. ^a GC yield. ^b Isolated yield.

Catalytic systems comprising inexpensive non-noble metal catalyst have also been reported. In 2013, Shimizu and co-workers found an alumina-supported nickel catalyst,¹⁷³ which gave good selectivity for primary amines directly from alcohols and ammonia under relatively mild conditions without any additives. The possibility of amination of various secondary and primary alcohols was also examined. As shown in Figure 19, various cyclic aliphatic secondary alcohols were selectively converted to the corresponding primary amines with

good to high yield (77–96%) and for the amination of primary alcohols, moderate yields of the corresponding primary amines (70, 78%) were obtained. Following this work, in 2014 this group found nickel nanoparticles loaded onto calcium silicate (Ni/CaSiO₃) as a more effective catalyst for direct synthesis of primary amines from alcohols and NH₃.¹⁷⁴ Various aliphatic alcohols were tolerated, and the turnover number (TON) was higher even than some Ru-based homogeneous catalysts. They also clarified that the surface Ni⁰ sites on small (3 nm) sized Ni nanoparticles are responsible for the high activity after detail studies with infrared (IR) investigation of the states of adsorbed CO and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Following these previous studies, Pera-Titus¹⁷⁵ then presented a study which focused on the selective synthesis of primary amines using alumina-ceria supported nickel formulations (Ni/CeO₂-Al₂O₃) based on very low nickel loading (2 wt%). After optimization, this catalyst afforded a comparable activity to the benchmark catalysts, but saving up to 75% Ni.

Figure 19 Amination of various alcohols with NH₃ by Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst. ^a GC yield. ^b Isolated yield.

Shi and co-workers¹⁷⁶ developed an air- and moisture-stable NiCuFeOx catalyst, which showed ample catalytic activity for the synthesis of N-substituted primary, secondary, tertiary, and cyclic amines using alcohols as the alkylation reagents and ammonia, primary amines, or secondary amines respectively, as the nitrogen source.

Esposito and co-workers¹⁷⁷ reported the reductive amination of different platform chemicals derived from cellulose using a carbonized filter paper-supported FeNi alloy catalyst that was used in a continuous flow reactor. Several bio-based platform chemicals such as HMF, furfural, and levulinic acid were converted to value-added products, including pyrrolidones from levulinic acid.

Recently Sels and co-workers¹⁷⁸ reported a novel heterogeneously catalyzed process - reductive aminolysis - in order to obtain short chain amines from carbohydrates at low temperature. In this process, commercial Ru and Ni catalysts were used and several high-value amines containing a bio-derived C2 carbon backbone (Figure 20) were synthesized in one step with yields up to 87% without solvent under mild reaction conditions (<132 °C).

Figure 20 Amines from glucose via reductive aminolysis reactions.

Nitriles

Catalytic conversion of alcohols to nitriles is an important transformation, since nitriles are versatile building blocks.^{179,180} Recent research has focused on the development of easily reusable and cost-efficient heterogeneous catalysts. In 2014, Beller and co-workers prepared a nitrogen-doped graphene supported cobalt and iron oxide-based nanocatalyst.¹⁸¹ These catalysts showed great activity for the synthesis of aromatic, heterocyclic and aliphatic nitriles from alcohols and aqueous ammonia using molecular oxygen as oxidant (Figure 21 a). According to this procedure, this group obtained adiponitrile, an important precursor of the nylon 6,6 polymer by using 1,6-hexanediol which can be derived from the sugar fraction of biomass (Figure 21) as substrate.

Figure 21 a) General reaction pathway for the synthesis of nitriles from alcohols and b) Synthesis of adiponitrile from biomass derived 1,6-hexanediol. ^a isolated yield.

Inspired by previous reports, we have first attempted the coupling of ammonia with the aliphatic alcohol moiety of **1G** via the borrowing hydrogen strategy, however the selectivity to the primary amine turned out to be insufficient, due to expected competing pathways, such as the formation of the dialkylation product. Furthermore, when using extra hydrogen gas to facilitate imine reduction, loss of the alcohol moiety was observed due to competing hydrogenolysis or additional decarbonylation pathways. However, using ammonia directly and commercially available Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst, and in the absence of hydrogen gas, formation of the corresponding nitrile (**9G**) was found via two consecutive dehydrogenation

steps as shown in Figure 22. The nitrile **9G** was obtained in very good selectivity (about 90%) at full conversion and a good 68% isolated yield. The potential areas of application of all derived compounds are also shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22 Reaction network for the catalytic conversion of **1G** to a range of useful chemicals. Reaction steps from **1G** to nitrile **9G** The aldehyde and imine intermediates *en route* to formation of **9G** via dehydrogenation and amination reaction.

The obtained versatile nitrile building block could be hydrolyzed to the corresponding acid, which in turn underwent catalytic decarboxylation to the styrene derivative in good yield. This compound can be potentially used directly as polymer building blocks or subjected to olefin cross metathesis to obtain the stilbene that potentially serves as sustainable bisphenol. The acid could also be converted to the cyclic indanone from which the high volume drug Donepezil can be obtained in one step. Gratifyingly the desired primary amine was obtained in almost analytical purity directly by hydrogenation of the nitrile **9G**. Using the same Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst, hydrogenation of **1G** yielded 4-ethyl-guaiacol (**3G**) that was further converted to aniline derivatives by homogeneous Ni catalyzed cross coupling to a range of compounds summarized in Figure 23. Further direct catalytic phenol to aniline transformation has however proven very challenging and should be addressed in future research.

Figure 23 Value-added chemicals by catalytic transformation **1G** and **3G**. ^a isolated yields.

With the aim to develop efficient methods to convert lignin into high-value chemicals, Li and co-workers developed a highly efficient palladium-catalysed reaction between anilines and phenol as lignin model monomer.¹⁸² In this system, inexpensive sodium formate was used as the hydrogen donor. A series of secondary and tertiary substituted cyclohexylamines were obtained under mild conditions in moderate to excellent yields.

4. Conclusion and outlook

Herein we summarized our recent advances in the use of doped metal oxides as well as other, mainly heterogeneous catalysts for the conversion of lignocellulose to a range of products including alkanes and functionalized aromatic building blocks. The global strategy follows depolymerization pathways that maintain some of the inherent complexity of the renewable starting material and allow to access alcohol intermediates that are ideally set up for further, sustainable and waste-free catalytic transformations involving C-C bond formation and C-N bond formation.

The presented *LignoFlex*, full reductive lignocellulose depolymerization process and the related downstream processing pathways are merely a first example for the “cleave and couple” concept. In the future the available pool of platform chemicals will be extended by various other intermediates bearing alternative functional groups (e.g. olefins, ketones/aldehydes, acids). This will also require the functionalization pathways to be adjusted in order to access a wider variety of products. In order to increase the available pool of platform chemicals, several challenging transformations still have to be tackled, for example the scission of strong C-C bonds. In order to access a wider variety of products, several “dream reactions” should be developed, such as the direct phenol to aniline transformation or activation of aromatic $-OCH_3$ groups to undergo cross coupling reactions to form C-N or C-C bonds. Selective and efficient demethoxylation or demethylation reactions are also highly desired.

It would be ideal to join several reaction steps in tandem, one-pot processes, opening possibilities for the design of elaborate catalyst systems for example at the interface (or the combination) of homogeneous/heterogeneous catalysis or in combination with alternative solvents e.g. multifunctional task-specific ionic liquids. Alternative reaction media can be used to aid feedstock solubility as well as product separation. Several key challenges regarding industrial relevance, catalyst stability and robustness as well as tolerance to impurities present in lignocellulose raw material will need to be addressed in the future.

Due to the remarkable activity in the field of lignin depolymerization, next to the well-established cellulose-derived platform chemicals, novel aromatic small molecules originating from the lignin part have emerged. The next step is to extend our catalytic tools in order to enable efficient downstream processing in order to access tangible products and to integrate catalytic steps across the entire value chain.

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Table of contents

Cleave and couple: sustainable catalytic pathways to value added chemicals and fuels from lignocellulose.

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